

INACTIVATION OF PHOSPHORUS IN EUTROPHIC WATERS THROUGH THE APPLICATION OF MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract

The contamination of bodies of water generates a process of eutrophication, a phenomenon that causes an overflowing growth of algae and other plants, generating a deterioration in the quality of the water, in Ecuador, the lagoon of San Antonio de Padua, located northwest of the city of Riobamba is affected by this problem. In the present investigation, a sample of 6 liters of water was taken at a depth of 1 meter and stored in a previously sterilized amber glass bottle. Different analyzes were performed on the pre-treatment and post-treatment samples, which were: concentration of reactive phosphorus (P), chemical oxygen demand (COD), turbidity, and pH (field and laboratory). For the removal of phosphorus, three different treatments were prepared that consisted of adding 10mL (T₁), 20mL (T₂), and 40mL (T₃) of magnetite nanoparticles (50g·L⁻¹), in 300mL of extracted water; mixing and interaction in each treatment were carried out with 5 and 10 minutes of sonication using an ultrasonic processor, with the disappearance of aggregates that were observed at the bottom of the container, the gradual homogenization of the samples was verified. A triplicate of each treatment was carried out to determine the effect on the P adsorption efficiency by increasing the concentrations of magnetite NPs, and the effect that the interaction time has on the P removal efficiency, concluding that the use of NPMs as P adsorbing agent in different amounts and interaction times allows obtaining important inactivation ranges to improve water quality, reducing reactive P in different proportions.

Number: 10.14704/nq.2022.20.7.NQ33115

Neuro Quantology 2022; 20(7):908-916

1. Introduction

Anthropogenic activities generate a series of pollutants that reach aquifers and that, despite the existence of water treatment, cannot be eliminated, becoming an environmental and public health problem on a global scale. Derived from this problem, there is an excess of nutrients, such as phosphorus (essential for the growth of phytoplankton) in reservoirs and watercourses which, added to other factors such as hydrological changes or temperature

changes, can cause eutrophication, being one of the most common causes of deterioration of water quality due to the greater accumulation of organic matter and overgrowth of algae (le Moal et al., 2019; Wojtkowska & Bojanowski, 2021).

These blooms are not only capable of producing toxins and noxious odors but also lead to low dissolved oxygen which can lead to reduced biodiversity of fish and other aquatic species, although the effects of

eutrophication are easily visible, the process as such is complex and offers quantification difficulties, visual inspection techniques are used up to cutting-edge techniques such as marking with radioactive isotopes and satellite information technology (García Miranda & Miranda Rosales, 2018).

Determining nutrient loads that can be assimilated by the water body can be difficult because, unlike other specific substances, a certain amount of nutrients is essential to sustain aquatic life (Abell et al., 2019). According to this, there is a need to control the excessive input of nutrients and other parameters that can increase eutrophication, so it is important to trace the source of the nutrients (Bhagowati & Ahamad, 2019).

Phosphorus is found naturally in surface waters and is a basic compound that has an impact on the amount of biomass in water bodies. Under natural conditions, their circulation is regulated in a cycle and their total amount in ecosystems does not change significantly (Meyers & Strickler, 2019). In general, the phosphorus cycle is an important Earth system process that has varied over time, but specifically, the modern phosphorus cycle is dominated by agriculture and human activity. The natural river load of phosphorus has doubled due to increased fertilizer use, deforestation, soil loss, and sewage sources. This has led to the eutrophication of lakes and coastal areas, as mentioned above, and will continue to have an impact for several thousand years depending on future models of human activities (Filippelli, 2008).

Ramasahayam et al, 2014 mention that the removal of phosphorus from water is a global concern considering the harmful environmental effects of its excess since it can cause poor water quality and loss of aquatic life, to prevent because of the harmful environmental effects of excess phosphorus, several techniques have been devised to

remove it from wastewater. These techniques range from adsorption and precipitation to enhanced biological phosphorus removal. Adsorption and precipitation predominantly require the use of different metals in the phosphorus removal process (Ramasahayam et al., 2014).

Based on these procedures, it is possible to consider the use of magnetic iron nanoparticles (magnetite) for the inactivation of phosphorus in water, with eutrophic characteristics, becoming a method of restoring water quality, using the technique of high-gradient magnetic separation (Toala Cadena, 2019).

2. Materials and Methods

3.1. Chemicals

The chemicals used were $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Na_2SO_3 , $\text{Na}(\text{OH})$, and $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$ of reagent and analytical grade.

3.2. Synthesis of magnetite nanoparticles

Magnetic nanoparticles were synthesized by stoichiometric coprecipitation and surface absorption (Ormaza Hugo et al., 2019; Vera Moreno et al., 2018). $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$ was used as a protective surfactant against oxidation and aggregates in the solution. The nanoparticles were separated from the surfactant by decantation with distilled and filtered water, and then with a 0.2 Tesla magnet. The highest percentage of sizes obtained ranged between 10 and 30 nm, with a composition of 72.5% iron and 27.5% oxygen.

3.3. Electron microscopy of magnetite nanoparticles

The morphological information of the nanoparticles was studied with the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM/EDS) JEOL, JSM-IT100LA. The samples were prepared with a drop of ferrofluid in a sample holder and dried inside the SNOL flask, model 3/1100

LHM01. A dark double-sided carbon tape was then applied.

3.4. IR spectroscopy of magnetite nanoparticles

To identify the characteristic functional groups of the magnetite nanoparticles, the JASCO FT/IR-4100 IR spectroscope and the Spectra Manager software were used. The sample was prepared with distilled and filtered water with a drop of ferrofluid.

3.5. Collection and pre-processing of water samples.

The sampling was carried out in a lentic aquatic ecosystem, located in the province of Chimborazo-Ecuador, called "Laguna de San Antonio de Padua". The sampling methodology was according to the Ecuadorian Technical Standard (INEN), literal 4. A composite sample was taken with a total of 6 liters of water at a depth of 1 meter. The sample was stored in a previously sterilized amber glass bottle.

3.6. Evaluation of the trophic status of water samples

The following analyzes were performed on the pre-treatment and post-treatment samples: reactive P concentration, COD, turbidity, and pH (field and laboratory). The reactive P analysis was performed using the HACH photometer, DR 2800, and the amino acid method (8178), placing 10 mL of the sample in a solution of PHOSVER3 (Murphy & Riley, 1962). For the determination of COD, the HACH photometer, DR 2800, a reagent tube, and 2 mL of the sample were used under the following conditions: 160°C and 120 min. Turbidity was measured with the HACH Turbidimeter, RATIO XR, by the nephelometric method, with 20 mL of sample (Barter & Deas, 2003). The PH was determined in the field by the potentiometric method, with the use of the HANNA HI, 98128 pH meters, in the part closest to the center of

the "Laguna de San Antonio de Padua" and for the samples post-treatment, the pH was identified in the laboratory, with 20 mL of each sample.

3.7. Removal of P from water samples.

Three different treatments were prepared that consisted of adding 10mL (T₁), 20mL (T₂), and 40mL mL(T₃) of magnetite nanoparticles (50gL⁻¹) (Merino-Martos et al., 2011), in 300mL of water extracted from the "Laguna de San Antonio de Padua". Mixing and interaction in each treatment were carried out with 5 and 10 minutes of sonication using a SONICS Vibra Cell VC 505 / VC 750 ultrasonic processor, with 40% wave amplitude. With the disappearance of aggregates that were observed at the bottom of the container, the gradual homogenization of the samples was verified. A triplicate of each treatment was performed to determine the effect on P adsorption efficiency by increasing the concentrations of magnetite nanoparticles, and the effect of interaction time on P removal efficiency (de Vicente et al., 2010, 2011).

The removal efficiency of P (measured in %, Pr), which is specified as the relationship between the initial concentration of P and the concentration of adsorbed P, was determined by Eq. 1, as follows:

$$P_r = \frac{C_o - C_e}{C_o} \times 100 \text{ Ec. 1. (Gulati et al., 2008)}$$

Where P_r is the removal percentage. C_o is the initial concentration (mg/L) and C_e is the concentration of P after treatment.

3.8. Reuse of magnetite nanoparticles

Once the P adsorption process was completed and to obtain aggregates and dehomogenize, each sample was centrifuged. To remove the water from each post-treatment sample and prevent the flow of the nanoparticles, a 0.2 T magnet was used,

making them group in one place. The treated water was placed in amber bottles for further analysis. Ethyl alcohol with analytical quality was added to the retained nanoparticles, to preserve their properties (de Vicente et al., 2011).

3.9. Statistical analysis

Through a Mixed Factor Analysis, a study of the experimental units was carried out to verify, through the Greenhouse-Geisser test, if the suspension of nanoparticles and the interaction time significantly influence the physicochemical parameters analyzed. The data obtained after 5 and 10 minutes of interaction with 10, 20, and 40 mL of suspension to which the samples were

exposed were considered in the analysis. For statistical analysis, SPSS software was used.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Identification of nanoparticles

The spectrogram (Figure 1.) obtained using IR spectroscopy shows the characteristic absorption bands for the most common functional groups present in iron NPMs. The most important is the hydroxyl group (O-H), represented by the band 3310.21 cm^{-1} ; and the $654,715\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band which is a characteristic vibration produced by Fe-O-Fe stretching (Fathi et al., 2019; Flores-Urquizo et al., 2017; Shurvell, 2006)

Figure 1. Spectrogram of the iron NPMs. Characteristic absorption bands for the most common functional groups present in iron NPMs.

4.2. Morphology and size of nanoparticles

To determine if nanoparticles were obtained with the synthesis process, the samples were visualized through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with a magnification of $10\ \mu\text{m}$, a voltage of 12.0 kV, and a viscosity of 1675 cps. The images were analyzed with Image J software, and morphological information was obtained (Image 1) corresponding to the nanoparticles. With the analysis it was determined that; the nanoparticles have an amorphous crystalline structure; 63% have a size ranging between

10 and 30 nm, with a mean value of 15 nm; 14% between 31 and 50 nm; 13% between 51 and 70 nm and 10% have a size between 71 and 100 nm. It can be deduced that the surfactant acts correctly and positively influences the morphological properties of the magnetic nanoparticles. In addition, the amount of reagent allows the generation of sufficient interactions to create the precursor salt of the NPMs (Ormaza Hugo et al., 2020).

Image 1: SEM magnification 10000x. Micrograph showing the formation of iron nanocrystals (magnetite).

4.3. Trophic status of water samples

Table 1 shows the pretreatment characteristics of the waters from the "San Antonio de Padua" Lagoon determined by physical-chemical and biological analysis. The concentration of reactive phosphorus, when measuring the amount of dissolved or particulate orthophosphates in organic and inorganic form, and being a limiting nutrient of primary production, is a determinant of the trophic status of the aquatic system under study (Arocena & Conde, 1999; Wetzel, 2001). With chlorophyll-a, the variations of the phytoplankton biomass, directly responsible for the health of the ecosystem, were identified. With this, an immediate response to the variability of the nutrients was obtained.

Table 1: Analyzed parameters of the water sample and determination of the trophic state.
^a(Diana et al., 2010)

Parameter	Unity		Value	Trophic State
Chlorophyll-a	(mg/L)		35.2	γ Eutrophic ^a
pH	-		10.14	
Turbidity	(NTU)		11.13	
Reactive Phosphorus	(mg/L)		0.17	β Eutrophic ^a
COD	(mg/L)		48	

4.4. Phosphorus adsorption and removal

Considering that the COD allows evaluating the strength of waste (Espinosa Chávez et al., 2016). Figure 2.A. shows its evolution with an interaction time of 5 and 10 minutes. After 5 minutes, mean values of 47, 58, and 63 mg/L are observed in the samples treated with suspensions of 10, 20, and 40 mL of NPMs, respectively. While, with 10 minutes of interaction, the greatest increase (128 mg/L) is reflected with the 10 mL suspension. With this we can affirm that, the greater the contact time to which the medium is subjected, the increase in COD will be more notable. This, considering that the level of inorganic substances susceptible to being oxidized increases, thus evidencing the need to carry out physical purification at the time of obtaining the NPMs.

The evolution of the turbidity in the water samples (Figure 2.B.), indicates that the effect of the treatment for the adsorption of P with the suspension of 20 mL of ferrofluid; with contact times of 5 and 10 minutes, with results of 8.17 and 8.13 NTU respectively, it presents better results. It is then assumed that the number of phytoplankton and material in suspension has an acceptable decrease.

Figure 2.C. shows the pH values once the suspensions have been applied and after the contact time. With 10 mL of suspension, the pH is reduced to 7.3, while the values (lower 8.4, higher 8.7) with 20 and 40 mL of ferrofluid are similar (mean 8.5). What is indicated is strengthened by the results

shown according to the amount of suspension of NPMs. In addition, since pH is a growth factor for many organisms and its value has a great influence on eutrophication, when it is acid (Huang et al., 2017), the effectiveness

that the application of NPMs can have been clear in the treatment of eutrophic waters (de Vicente et al., 2010).

Figure 2. Parameters were analyzed after treatments with suspensions of 10, 20, and 40 mL.

Variation of each parameter concerning

the initial analysis of the water sample. The circles show the initial value, and the triangles, the values with 5 min. of interaction and the squares with 10 min.

The variation in the concentration of P at different pH levels that is observed in Figure 3., shows that, in the treatment carried out with 40 mL of suspension with an interaction time of 5 minutes, the elimination of P reaches 88.2%. with a concentration of 0.02

mg/L. Results like those obtained by Merino-Martos et al., in which the phosphorus level decreased by 72% in a similar treatment with NPMs (Merino-Martos et al., 2015). Note that, with smaller amounts of ferrofluid suspension; in this case 20 and 10 mL, the percentage of phosphorus removed is reduced to values of up to 47.1% and 35.3% respectively. In the treatments with an interaction time of 10 minutes, with 40 mL of suspension, a reduction of up to 94.1% is achieved, also observing that, with smaller amounts of ferrofluid, the elimination of P

from the samples is affected as in the previous case (interaction of 5 min). Due to the origin of the NPMs, the amount of suspension modifies the pH. Then, the relationship between the amount of ferrofluid and interaction time, with the elimination of P is inversely proportional, as also shown by the analysis of intra-subject effects with the intervention of both factors. Values of $p=0.000$ and $p=0.006$, imply that the time and suspension of NPMs significantly influenced the analyses.

Figure 3. Percentage of P removal (P_r %) according to the amount of ferrofluid and its incidence in the variation of the pH of the treated samples. The squares indicate the P_r with 5 min. of interaction and the triangles with 10 min. similar P_r with the same amount of suspension.

5. Conclusions.

The variation of controllable parameters such as temperature and agitation time in the synthesis process provides information on the surface adsorption process through the Co-precipitation method, which allowed for obtaining stable samples in size and structure.

Chemical oxygen demand did not interfere with P adsorption efficiency, despite being one of the highest levels reported for inactivation with NPMs in eutrophic waters.

The use of NPMs as an inactivating agent for P from eutrophicated water bodies, in different quantities and interaction times,

allows obtaining important inactivation ranges to improve water quality, reducing reactive phosphorus in different proportions.

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